

Corrigendum to

“Heavy rainfall episodes over Liguria in autumn 2011: numerical forecasting experiments” published in *Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 14, 1325–1340, 2014

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In the paper “Heavy rainfall episodes over Liguria in autumn 2011: numerical forecasting experiments” by A. Buzzi et al. (*Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci.*, 14, 1325–1340, doi:10.5194/nhess-14-1325-2014, 2014) an error occurred in Table 4. The dates in the first column were incorrect. The correct table should be as follows:

Table 4. As Table 3 but for the GE event.

Initial analysis	18 h accumulated precipitation (mm), 4 November 2011, 03:00–21:00 UTC
ECMWF-IFS, 20111103, 12:00 UTC	190
NOAA-GFS, 20111103, 12:00 UTC	140
ECMWF-IFS, 20111104, 00:00 UTC	266
NOAA-GFS, 20111104, 00:00 UTC	248